

INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL LEGAL MODELS FOR COMBATING UNFAIR COMPETITION: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract.

This article analyzes the problem of unfair competition within the framework of both international and national legal systems. Using the examples of the USA, Germany, France, Japan, Canada, and others, the author explores legal mechanisms, legislative approaches, and practical differences in combating unfair competition. The article compares broad and narrow interpretations of the concept and classifies countries into three legal groups based on their regulatory approach. It also addresses the legal uncertainty surrounding unfair competition, forms of liability, and the need for legal adaptation in the context of the digital economy. The findings emphasize the importance of integrating international best practices into national antitrust policy frameworks.

Keywords: unfair competition, competition law, antitrust legislation, monopoly, international law, legal mechanisms, digital economy, legal harmonization, case law, state policy

In both international and the majority of national markets, the dominance of a market economy has been established. Within this system, the issue of methods and means of competitive struggle for market share among business entities is becoming increasingly relevant. Every year, we witness an intensifying economic competition among these entities, as each one strives to achieve a common primary objective in its activity — to gain the highest possible profit through the sale of its goods or services. Nowadays, more and more unlawful practices are emerging that aim to disrupt the balance of fair market competition¹.

In other words, every business entity seeks to win in the competitive struggle against others. Unfortunately, in this pursuit, the interests of the state, business partners, and most importantly, the rights of the key subject in market relations — the consumer — are often ignored, which is unacceptable and unnatural. One of the fundamental goals of market trade is to satisfy the needs of the consumer; otherwise, the transaction cannot occur. There are many parameters of competition and, consequently, many ways to win, and not all of them are unlawful. The law restricts the freedom of the seller or producer only

¹ Fajar M. Fair competition: The concept of regulation in the sharing economy //The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business. – 2020. – T. 7. – №. 11. – C. 637-645.

in cases where their actions cause harm to other participants in the trade system (initially targeting rival enterprises, but ultimately affecting the consumer). In such cases, we are dealing with a direct violation of legal norms.

Each national legislature on the international stage faces the task of establishing frameworks that restrict the activities of business entities to ensure that such activities do not cause legal or actual harm to the state, society, or individual members of society — namely, consumers, that is, the citizens of the state².

From a legal and technical standpoint, the institution of combating unfair competition occupies a different position within the legal systems of various countries. In some states (e.g., the USA, Japan, and Canada), the norms on combating unfair competition are integrated into antitrust legislation, as unfair competition itself is viewed as one of the elements of monopolistic practices.

Within the framework of laws targeting monopolistic practices, specific types of violations are identified and characterized as unfair competition. However, such regulation can be considered more closed and limited, which, especially today, may lead to the legislation lagging behind the current realities due to rapid changes in various spheres, including entrepreneurship. In other countries, particularly in Common Market states (such as those of the EU), this legal institution forms an independent branch of civil and administrative law regulation, functioning alongside specialized antitrust legislation, referred to there as legislation against restrictive business practices. The regulatory framework is thus represented by different legal acts.

In the context of this scholarly article, it is important to examine the global experience of legal regulation in countering unfair competition. For the purpose of improving the existing systems of legal regulation within national antitrust legislation, it is of great significance to study and adopt the positive foreign experience in this field and, as a result, to apply the most successful models of international legal planning and regulation of various areas of competitive legal relations.

For example, in France, the system of protection against unfair competition is built on the general provisions of civil legislation. It is worth noting that this deprives the law of flexibility and precision, forcing judges to seek analogies and apply general civil norms that are not always adaptable to entrepreneurial relations. Regarding compensation for damage caused by unlawful actions in this context, a law was adopted in France in 1905, the essence of which is to

² Stiglitz J. E. Regulating multinational corporations: Towards principles of cross-border legal framework in a globalized world balancing rights with responsibilities //Am. U. Int'l L. Rev. – 2007. – T. 23. – C. 451.

combat fraud in the process of product distribution. This law was later supplemented by a number of regulatory acts, such as those on misleading advertising broadcasts, the law on consumer information, and others.

In Germany, the key legal act remains the "Law Against Unfair Competition" (Gesetz gegen den unlauteren Wettbewerb), which contains general provisions on dishonest commercial practices in the economic market. Based on this legal act, German courts have developed extensive case law, which has formed a system of suppression of unfair competition aimed at protecting the interests of the market, the state, society, and consumers³.

Germany's adopted antitrust regulation somewhat differs from the typical Western European model because it has a mixed nature. As a general rule, it provides for a total ban on monopolies, but there are many exceptions to this prohibition. This provides a basis for the Russian legal system to borrow certain types of exceptions and methods of regulating the activities of natural monopolies.

For example, a rather interesting exception is the granting of authority to the German Minister of Economy to authorize transactions that, under other circumstances, would be considered illegal due to anti-competitive restrictions, but in this case, the minister determines that the economic benefits outweigh the illegality of the restriction and justifies the action.

When examining the position of the United States of America in the context of countering unfair competition, it should be noted that court decisions based on the precedent system of law play a key role⁴. These decisions are based on the state-level legislative acts aimed at suppressing unfair business practices, which gives the legal system greater flexibility and adaptability to the dynamic conditions of modern reality. Similarly, in England, case law in the area of combating unfair competition has been developed by judicial bodies.

Let us draw attention to the lack of uniformity in the context of defining unfair competition. In practice, unfair competition refers to the actions of competing economic entities in relation to one another when evaluating such subjective criteria as "good morals," "good faith," "fair custom," and so on. This approach is enshrined both in international treaties and in the national legislation of specific countries.

³ Möllers T. M. J. Enforcement of Unfair Competition Law by Notice of Violation, Rights of Consumers and Public Authorities—Comparative Evaluation of the German Status Quo //Patents and Technological Progress in a Globalized World: Liber Amicorum Joseph Straus. – Berlin, Heidelberg : Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009. – C. 413-429.

⁴ Burn C. The National Law of Unfair Competition //Harvard Law Review. – 1949. –T. 62. – №. 6 – C. 987-1001.

Characterizing national legislation, it should be noted that a broad understanding generally prevails, in which the concept of unfair competition encompasses a wide variety of actions by competing business entities aimed at monopolizing the market for their own goods or services. It is not feasible to adopt a ready-made model of regulation solely from international instruments, yet the general direction of legal development in this area is clear.

This understanding corresponds to a specific construction of national legal systems, where rules on unfair competition can operate simultaneously with general provisions of civil law and antitrust legislation. Additionally, protection of violated rights can be carried out through various legal remedies. A narrow interpretation of the concept of unfair competition should not be excluded either, which includes specific types of dishonest behavior by competing businesses⁵.

Currently, several groups of countries have formed, each reflecting a particular approach to the protection against unfair competition — in other words, those states where measures to combat unfair competition are undertaken.

Researchers have identified three key groups. The first group includes those countries that have adopted specialized laws addressing unfair competition. These countries typically enact general prohibitions on unfair competition and provide a non-exhaustive list of acts considered unfair. Countries in this group include: Germany; Austria; Switzerland

Some other countries, such as Canada and Japan, also fall under this category, as they provide similar frameworks, even if the legal form differs.

The second group includes countries that lack specialized legislation defining the concept of unfair competition. In these countries, regulation is based on provisions of civil codes supplemented by court practice. Examples include: Italy; The Netherlands⁶;

The third group encompasses those countries whose legislation does not clearly differentiate between the rules governing unfair competition and antitrust regulation. These include: France; The United States; The United Kingdom; Ireland; Russia; Austria and a number of other nations.

Meanwhile, it is interesting to note that the first countries to adopt antitrust legislation were the United States and Canada, whose antimonopoly laws remain at a rather high level to this day, despite the fact that these two countries fall

⁵ Sellers M. N. S. The doctrine of precedent in the United States of America //Am. J. Comp. L. – 2006. – T. 54. – C. 67.

⁶ Charny D. Competition among jurisdictions in formulating corporate law rules: An American perspective on the race to the bottom in the European communities //Harv. Int'l. LJ. – 1991. – T. 32. – C. 423.

into different regulatory groups. Thus, unfair competition is a problem faced by the majority of countries, which is why the prohibition of such conduct exists not only at the national level within each country but also at the international level.

Unfair competition through deception, much like discreditation, involves the dissemination of false information to consumers about a product. However, in cases of deception, the distortion of information pertains specifically to one's own product with the aim of drawing more attention to it and increasing its demand.

Countries address this problem through various legal means, which differ depending on the legal system, national mentality, and economic conditions. Nevertheless, a unified general concept has already been established and enshrined in international treaties, and cooperation with countries that have either a similar legal regulatory system to that of the Russian Federation or a different one can significantly advance Russian competition (antitrust) legislation..

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